

THE KEY ROLE OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL STRATEGIES ON IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION IN PRESIDENTIAL SCHOOLS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article deals with pedagogical strategies for improving the quality of education in the Presidential schools and their impact on the educational process of students, consistent monitoring and management of the educational process in the Presidential schools.*

Keywords: *pedagogical strategies, culture, administrative management, leadership skills.*

Firstly, we should pay our attention to the importance of innovative pedagogical strategies which involve special introduction to ordinary teaching style today we are slowly and step by step refusing by analyzing the drawbacks of teacher-oriented approach. At the same time nowadays globalization process around the world is getting faster and faster, in turn, is being considered by our government as the most important mission of the agenda of preparing globally competitive and knowledgeable specialists. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev specified the role of education in his books, speeches and live meetings with scientists. After all, the ideas and teachings of scholars such as Bukhari and Termizi, Farabi and Ferghani, Ibn Sina and Al-Khwarizmi, Ulugbek and Navoi, who were born and raised in the territory of our country on the basis of the specific values of our culture formed in our republic, universal human principles, scientific and theoretical aimed at the spiritual enlightenment of young people's views and the fact that our country has passed a new stage of development and its contributions to the entire world civilization are incomparable. As a proof of this, the research of this scientific and cultural heritage, scientific research, in turn, is reflected in the works of our president.

Recently, on the date August 28 of 2023 year there held a live videos meeting of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev on "Priority tasks for further improving the quality of education in schools, increasing the number of students and improving the qualifications of teachers and creating suitable conditions for them". Our president paid a special attention to education system of pre-school and school education with his highly motivated speech.

Furthermore, main document of Presidential schools of Uzbekistan, a decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on approval of the statute on Presidential schools on June 25, 2019, No. 526 says that schools are integrated to SCL and by using innovative pedagogical strategies government target on higher results.

While we are striving to prepare globally competitive and knowledgeable specialists, there are some key factors which we should really take into the consideration. They are the following ones:

Innovative pedagogical strategies

Qualified and competitive staff

Leadership skills for administrative management

Now we would like emphasize the importance of innovative pedagogical strategies such as the newly introduced student –centered approach of teaching method.

When a high school student Andres first arrived at Círculos, an XQ school in Santa Ana, CA, he wasn't sure what to think. "I was skeptical when I first looked at it because it was so different from traditional high schools," he said. "It was a classroom without walls."

It's true that Círculos does class differently: at school, students sit in circles instead of typical rows of desks, and have significant flexibility in their schedules. And like Andres noticed, a large portion of learning takes place through projects in the community, outside the traditional classroom. These structural features are all part of Círculos's commitment to empowering and engaging students through student-centered learning.

Like the name implies, student-centered learning (SCL) makes students co-creators of their own education, engaging them in decisions about what, when, and how they learn. In doing so, SCL helps high schools prepare students not only with academic knowledge, but also with the skills of self-direction, curiosity, creativity, and collaboration they'll need for future success. As Andres described the end of his time at Círculos: "They were always so open. 'You want to do this? OK, let's do it.' They really taught me to be flexible and adaptable. That helped me grow beyond the classroom."

As we see above experience of a high school student Andres, we can observe the benefits of student-centered learning which differs from teacher-centered one significantly. Here is given the differentiation of teacher and student centered learning approaches (Figure 1).

In the meantime, our students enjoy feeling themselves independent and free to speak and express their own opinions as well as sharing their knowledge with their classmates.

Figure 1: Differentiation of teacher and student centered learning approaches

Defining Student-Centered Learning

Students succeed when what they're learning matters to them. In student-centered learning, students' interest drives education. Student-centered learning gives students the opportunity to decide two things: what material they learn and how they learn it. (This concept is also sometimes referred to as personalized learning.) In contrast to teacher-centered approaches, SCL engages

students as leaders and decision-makers in their own learning. For example, at Purdue Polytechnic High School in Indianapolis, IN, students engage in SCL in their Foundations class, as they solve real-world challenges posed by community partners—for example, how students would support a future world with 9.5 billion people living on it. Students plan their own research, propose a solution, communicate their ideas to teachers and community members, and evaluate their own progress as they go. Teachers help guide this process, but the content, timing, and motivation is down to students themselves.

As SCL is so personalized for each student and community, it can take many different forms. However, successful SCL programs share these some common features:

- Emphasis on project-based, interdisciplinary learning
- Deep connection between curriculum and student interests
- Assessment as a tool to measure learning and help students grow
- Meaningful feedback platforms for students and families
- Learning plans tailored to individual students
- Flexibility and adaptability—especially evident during the shift to virtual learning

What does student-centered learning actually feel like to students? Here is given an experience of Jada Johnson, a graduating senior from Brooklyn Laboratory High School, offered this reflection: “Teachers viewed scholars as more than students. ... We were treated as individuals with our own ideas and viewpoints, and that were incorporated into classes and school governance. Brooklyn Lab gave me the strength to use my voice. Now, I’m not afraid to stand up and speak my opinion.”

When we see the below given chart, we can easily see the main advantages of SCL and earnings from it by performing enough abilities which are really make our classes more achievable and interesting.

Using the tenets of and the instructional cycle for student-centered learning, the paper goes on to explore some of the primary uses of technology for supporting students and teachers. In the paragraphs following the tables, the implications for parents, advisors, mentors/internship supervisors, school leadership, and district leadership are considered. At the center of all of these descriptions sits the focus on optimizing student learning through a variety of personalized tools, resources, strategies, collaboration and the use of robust data reporting and technology.

Users of a student-centered learning integrated system will have different needs dependent upon the user’s role and the model(s) of student-centered learning being implemented. These needs should be the basis for the design and selection of technology systems within the integrated system. Figure-2 shows Instructional Cycle for Student-Centered Learning by Liz Glowa.

On the whole, we can surely say that, most existing IT systems used in schools were implemented to support a teacher and course-centric approach, as well as compliance reporting for basic student data, course-taking, grades and scheduling data in a time-based system, however, using the innovative pedagogical strategies on improving the quality of education in Presidential schools in Uzbekistan. At the same time, during the observation process of the school, we encountered the tendency of SCL in classes performing by international teachers as mostly approved and appreciated by the students.

The survey shows that, innovative pedagogical strategies are welcomed not only by students or teaching staff, but also administration to manage and control the educational process of the school.

Figure-2 : Instructional Cycle for Student-Centered Learning by Liz Glowa.

REFERENCES

1. Collections of selected works of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev-2019 year.
2. On the Strategy of Actions for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947. February 7, 2017
3. Video selector meeting of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoyev on "Priority tasks for further improving the quality of education in schools, increasing the number of students and improving the qualifications of teachers and creating suitable conditions for them". August 28, 2023
4. A decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on approval of the statute on Presidential schools. June 25, 2019, No. 526
5. Abdullaeva B.S. Methodological and didactic foundations of interdisciplinarity (in the example of teaching mathematics in academic lyceums in social and humanitarian directions): *Ped. science. Ph.D. Diss. abstract.* - T., 2006, -63 p
6. Muminov O, N -Prezident maktablarida ta'lim sifatini oshirishning pedagogik strategiyalari , *Toshkent Davlat Pedagogika Universiteti Ilmiy Axborotlari Ilmiy-Nazariy Jurnal*, ISSN 2181-9580 , 2023 yil 8-son, 355-362 b

7. Muminov O, N- Prezident maktablarida o'quv-tarbiya jarayonini tashkil etishning pedagogik-didaktik va normativ asoslari, *Toshkent Davlat Pedagogika Universiteti Ilmiy Axborotlari Ilmiy-Nazariy Jurnal*, ISSN 2181-9580 , 2023 yil 9-son, 102-108 b.
8. Muminov O, N- Prezident maktablarida ta'lim sifatini oshirishda pedagogik strategiyalarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari , *Toshkent Davlat Pedagogika Universiteti Ilmiy Axborotlari Ilmiy-Nazariy Jurnal*, ISSN 2181-9580 , 2023 yil 9-son, 143-153b
9. Muminov O, N- Yangilanayotgan O'zbekiston sharoitida Prezident maktablarida ta'lim sifatini rivojlantirish holati, *Toshkent Davlat Pedagogika Universiteti Ilmiy Axborotlari Ilmiy-Nazariy Jurnal*, ISSN 2181-9580 , 2023 yil 9-son, 131-138 b
10. Muminov Obidkhon Norkhujayevich- PEDAGOGICAL STRATEGIES FOR IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION IN PRESIDENTIAL SCHOOLS IN UZBEKISTAN , *SCIENCE AND INNOVATION*
11. *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL* UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337 | SCIENTISTS.UZ VOLUME 2 ISSUE 9 SEPTEMBER 2023
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8364128>
12. Muminov O, -Increasing tourist attraction to Uzbekistan in digital economy period by enhancing service quality, 2023/8/1, *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability (EJRDS)*, Volume-4, ISSN: 2660-55, pages 13-15, editor <https://www.scholarzest.com>
13. Muminov O,- Development of hospitality industry by improving service quality and customer satisfaction in Uzbekistan,2021, ISBN: 978-93-96573-28-3 Published by Novateur Publication 466, Sadashiv Peth, M.S.India-411030
<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=aOilsJQAAAAAJ&hl=ru>
14. Obidkhon, Norkhujayevich Muminov- ВЛИЯНИЕ НА УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ И ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬЮ , 2021/11 , *Xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda zamonaviy texnologiyalarning muammolari va istiqbollari* , Том 1, Номер 2 , Страницы 53-63, О'ZBEKISTON JURNALISTIKA VA OMMAVIY KOMMUNIKATSIYALAR UNIVERSITETI
15. Obidkhon, Norkhujayevich Muminov, Muxridin Nasridinov Vaslidin o'g'li - Comparative Typology of Verbal Means Expressing the Concept of "Goal" in Languages with Different Systems , *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF LITERATURE, PHILOSOPHY AND CULTURE* Volume: 02 Issue: 12 December 2021
16. Liz Glowa- What Are the Implications of Student-Centered Learning for Technology? EDUCATION DOMAIN BLOG, Issues in Practice: June 2, 2016
17. Anna Sudderth- What Is Student Centered Learning and Why Is It Important? EDUCATION DOMAIN BLOG, Issues in Practice: August 16th , 2018